

Photocatalytic reaction of vanillin oxime and salicylaldehyde oxime by TiO₂ semiconductor

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TiO₂-sensitized photo-oxidation of vanillin oxime and salicylaldehyde oxime has been studied. The increase in the polarity of the solvent increases yield of the photoproduct while increasing amounts of substrate and photocatalyst increase the yield of photoproduct only up to a certain limit. The rate of the reaction increases with the increase in the band gap of the semiconductor. A probable reasoning has been proposed giving structure-reactivity relationship of vanillin oxime and salicylaldehyde oxime with the isolated photoproduct. A reaction mechanism has been suggested.

The interest in heterogeneous catalysis is intense and increasing as shown by a large number of publications¹. More recently, there has been more interest in photocatalytic chemistry in connection with the role of photocatalyst in various biological systems for the development of novel compounds².

However, one area of semiconductor photocatalyst may have practical application in photo-oxidation of organic molecule which absorbs vis/UV radiations, can be photo-generated using various types of semiconductors via sensitization³. Semiconductors which are stable under photo-irradiation in aqueous medium, like TiO₂, ZnO, ZnS, SnO₂ carry current due to the flow of excess negative electrons, are *n*-type semiconductors⁴. The heterogeneous TiO₂ catalyst shows very strong oxidizing property in presence of oxygen⁵. Literature reveals that photo-oxidation of C=N bonded compounds like vanillin oxime and salicylaldehyde oxime is lacking in presence of such semiconductors^{6,7}. The present investigation was undertaken with the view that it can be used as such or as a model system for evaluating the efficiency of photocatalytic reaction and also the mechanistic aspects like lifetime and modes of reaction etc. on microinterfaces on UV-illumination⁸.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of the analytical, chemical and spectral (IR, mass) data the products were characterized as vanillin and salicylaldehyde. The control experiments were carried out (i) in presence of photocatalyst without exposure to UV-light and (ii) in presence of UV-light but without photocatalyst. In both the cases photoproduct was not obtained, thus confirming the necessity of both components for this reaction.

The yields of the photoproducts increased up to 0.200 g of the substrate (vanillin oxime 24%, salicylaldehyde oxime

20%) and further increase in the amount of substrate showed very low increase in the yields of the photoproducts (25 and 21%, respectively). The rate of photocatalytic reaction was found to be constant with increasing concentration of substrate, where more substrate molecules are available to hinder the movement of substrate molecules towards the semiconductor surface⁹. Various solvents of different dielectric constant were used to study the effect of solvent on the rate of photocatalytic reaction. The rate of reaction increased with increasing polarity of the solvent (Table 1). This suggests that some polar species are involved in this photocatalytic reaction as an intermediate. The yields of photoproducts increased up to 0.200 g of the photocatalyst (vanillin oxime 24%, salicylaldehyde oxime 20%). This observation may be explained on the basis that at the initial stage, even a small addition of photocatalyst increases the yields of photoproducts as the surface area of photocatalyst increase, but after a certain limit (0.200 g), the surface at the bottom of the reaction vessel becomes completely covered with photocatalyst. Now, increase in the amount of photocatalyst will only increase the thickness of the layer of photocatalyst already formed at the bottom of the vessel. Hence, the yields of the photoproducts remain unaffected by addition of the photocatalyst above a certain limit.

Table 1. Effect of polarity of solvent

Substrate = 0.200 g, photocatalyst(TiO₂) = 0.200 g, time of irradiation = 600 min, solvent = 50 ml

Solvent	Dielec. const. <i>D</i>	% Yield of photoproduct for	
		Vanillin oxime	Salicylaldehyde oxime
1-Butanol	17.10	20.0	14.0
Isopropanol	18.30	22.0	15.0
Ethanol	24.30	23.0	18.0
Methanol	32.63	24.0	20.0

The effect of nature of photocatalyst on the yield of photoproduct was also studied. It was observed that when UV-light was employed as source for irradiation, the yield of photoproduct increased with the band gap of semiconductor. The yield was higher in the presence of ZnS and relatively low in the presence of TiO₂ (Table 2). It can be explained that the semiconductor having higher band gap absorbs more efficiently in UV-light, and injects electrons into the conduction band more rapidly which are used for oxidation of organic compound.

Table 2. Effect of nature of photocatalyst

Substrate = 0.200 g, photocatalyst(TiO₂) = 0.200 g, time of irradiation = 600 min, solvent (methanol) = 50 ml

Photocatalyst	Band gap eV	% Yield of photoproduct for	
		Vanillin oxime	Salicylaldehyde oxime
TiO ₂	3.1	24.0	20.0
ZnO	3.2	27.0	23.0
SnO ₂	3.5	29.0	27.0
ZnS	3.6	30.0	29.0

On the basis of the above discussion the following probable mechanism has been proposed for the photocatalytic reaction of vanillin oxime and salicylaldehyde oxime. Metal oxide semiconductor TiO₂ behaves as short-circuited electrochemical cells where both cathodic and anodic electron transfer occur on the same particle. Excitation of TiO₂ (semiconductor) leads to the formation of an electron-hole pair,

Photo-excitation of TiO₂ produces a pair of electron and hole undergoing recombination without any chemical reaction in the absence of any suitable oxidant and/or reductant,

The hole reacts with oxime (vanillin oxime and salicylaldehyde oxime) as

while the electron converts oxygen O₂⁻ superoxide, a strong oxidizing species. So the presence of oxygen is necessary for photocatalytic oxidation,

Solvent having higher dielectric constant will enhance the formation of these intermediate stages, superoxide oxidizes [RR'C=NOH]⁺ into RR'C=O,

The overall view can be summarized in Scheme 1.

The mechanism is in confirmation with the photocatalytic reaction of dimethylglyoxime^{3,7}. Structure factors of vanillin oxime and salicylaldehyde oxime affect the rate of oxidation; due to the presence OCH₃ group the former increases the electron density of nucleus, resulting strongness of reactive centre as compared to the latter one, hence increase in the oxidizing rate. The mechanism gives structure-reactivity relationship.

Scheme 1. Illustration of the photocatalytic reaction of vanillin oxime and salicylaldehyde.

Experimental

Vanillin oxime and salicylaldehyde oxime (Merck) were purified by crystallization. TiO₂ (Merck), solvents like methanol, ethanol, isopropanol, 1-butanol (all B.D.H.) were used after checking purity. To the samples dissolved in solvent (50 ml), TiO₂ was added. The solution was then irradiated with near UV-light (Toshniwal λ-365 nm) kept at a distance of 20 cm from the upper surface of the reaction vessel. The progress of reaction was monitored with TLC at 2 h interval and the product identified. In initial stages of the reaction, only a single spot corresponding to parent compound was observed, when TLC plate was placed in iodine chamber. After 4 h of irradiation, TLC plate showed two spots, the one corresponding to parent compound and the other to the photoproduct. The reaction was allowed for completion (10 h). Photoproduct was separated (semicarbazone derivative, m.p. 239°) for vanillin oxime and (2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative, m.p. 252°) for salicylaldehyde oxime.

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